

GRAPHENE AND GRAPHENE OXIDE IN CONCRETE

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ABSTRACT

The article presents an experimental and theoretical study of graphite and graphite oxide in standard concrete. Improvement of the mechanical properties of concrete is noted at a concentration of (0.05 – 0.07)% of the concrete mass. A model of graphite splitting by aqueous solutions is obtained using only experimental data. A model of nanocracks in concrete is proposed. The length of a nanocrack is taken to be the thickness of the surface layer of a solid, which for metals is from 1 to 6 nm, and for standard concrete is about 60 nm, i.e. it is a nanostructure. For standard concrete: $L_{nm} = 60$ nm; $L_{\mu m} = 6$ microns; $L_C = 0.6$ mm. These data are typical without external load, without changing the environment. The number of cracks in concrete in the nanostructure region I is 10^5 , in the mesoscopic region II is 10^7 and in the pre-destruction region III is about 10^9 . The addition of graphene and graphene oxide to the cement mortar significantly strengthens (by 4-5 times) standard concrete and reduces the number of nanocracks/

Keywords: Graphene, graphene oxide, concrete, nanocrack, surface layer, nanostructure, destruction, catastrophe theory.

Introduction

Cracks in concrete, which determine their durability, have been studied for a very long time. Theoretical and experimental methods for studying cracks in concrete can be found in the latest dissertations, monographs and reviews [1-9]. But none of them talk about nanocracks, their length and their further development, up to the destruction of concrete.

The purpose of this article is to study the additives of graphene and graphene oxide in standard concrete and to propose a model for the formation of

nanocracks in concrete, the kinetics of their development up to its destruction.

Graphene concrete (brief review)

In 2004, a method for obtaining a single-atom layer of graphite, called graphene, was proposed in [10]. After this discovery, over 20 years, many studies have been conducted on the use of graphene in microelectronics, medicine, agriculture and in all areas of human activity. Concrete, which is indispensable in the construction of various structures [11] (Fig. 1), is no exception.

Figure 1. - Number of published articles on graphene and cement-based materials (a); schematic diagram of the graphene structure (b) [11].

From the published (over 3000) works on concrete, it follows that these works (in the majority) suffer from a drawback, namely: they do not control the number of graphene monolayers, and for natural graphite their number is 3 [12-14]. More than three graphene layers, it turns into graphite, and therefore there is a large difference in the studies conducted.

In accordance with the task, we will review the models of the incorporation of graphene or graphene

oxide into concrete. Let's start with work [15]. Graphene is treated with 98% H_2SO_4 and $NaNO_3$. The experimental results showed that with 0.03% graphene oxide-GO content, the cement composites exhibited an increase in tensile strength (78.6%), flexural strength (60.7%) and compressive strength (38.9%) compared with the conventional cement composites. Based on these results, the authors suggested that Ca_3SiO_5 , Ca_2SiO_4 and $Ca_3Al_2O_6$, which are the main ingredients

of anhydrous cement, preferentially react with the functional groups (-OH, -COOH and -SO₃H) on the surface

of GO. The hydration mechanism of GO cement is shown in Fig. 2.

Figure 2. - Schematic diagram of the mechanism of GO regulation on cement hydration crystals [15]. In [16], they put forward their theory about the mechanism of improving the material properties caused by GO. The authors claimed that graphene reacts with cement during the hydration process (Fig. 3). By measuring the thermal diffusivity, the authors indicated that the reaction between graphene and cement can improve the heat dissipation of concrete during the hydration process. This led to a decrease in thermal cracking in the samples, so that graphene can improve the strength of cementitious materials.

Figure 3. - Schematic diagram of the reaction between graphene and cement [16].

In [17], the mechanism of formation of the “flower-shaped” microstructure of hydration crystals was clarified, as shown in Fig. 4.

Figure 4. - Schematic diagram and SEM image of the hydration reaction of cement and the product [17].

The work [18] added another reason why graphene materials can improve the durability of concrete, as shown in Fig. 5:

Figure 5. Theoretical scheme of the binding of graphene oxide with chloride ions [18].

They suggest that the chemical crosslinking effect between divalent cations (such as calcium ions) and the surface functional groups of GO promotes the formation of Friedel salts (F salts). As a result, the chloride ion binding capacity of the cementitious material is increased. In addition, GO exhibits strong charge adsorption on calcium ions, effectively inhibiting the decomposition of F salt and making its structure more stable.

This finding suggests that the chloride curing property of graphene-modified concrete can help suppress the erosion by chloride ions. A model for inhibiting the occurrence of thermal cracks was proposed in [19] (Fig. 6).

Figure 6. - GO promotes crack repair and heat dissipation in concrete. (a) Principle of GO crack repair; (b) comparison of temperature profile of concrete mixed with rGO [19].

Samples for the study

The following components were used to prepare standard concrete: suspensions with GO – 3 pcs. (0.02% by weight, 0.05% by weight, 0.07% by weight); suspensions with rGO – 3 pcs. (0.02% by weight,

0.05% by weight, 0.07% by weight) a; cement M400 b; crushed stone with grain sizes of 5-20 mm c; sand grade M2.5-2.9 g; mixer VORONEZHFortis d; vibrating table e; concrete volume – 10 l (Fig. 7).

Figure 7. – Components for standard concrete

The obtained concrete samples were tested on PGM-2000MG4 (Fig. 8)

Figure 8. Concrete samples (a); PGM-2000MG4 press (b).

Research results

Final values of sample strength and strength dependence curve on GO concentration – 1 day (Fig. 9 and 10).

Measurement value	Control sample	0,02 %	0,05 %	0,07 %
Mass of a cube, g	2324	2337	2344	2337
Average weight, g	2316	2344	2333	2339
Density, g/cm ³	2,308	2,350	2,321	2,340
P1, MPa	17,29	19,6	20,33	22,37
P2, MPa	16,21	19,62	20,54	21,88
P _{avg} , MPa	16,75	19,63	20,44	22,13
P _{ref1} , %		17,10	22,00	32,09
P _{ref2} , %		1,17	1,22	1,32

Figure 9. - Tabulated results of strength tests of samples with graphene oxide.

Figure 10. - Relative error (P_{ref1}) of the strength of samples with GO depending on the control (a); dependence of the relative strength (P_{ref2}) in compression at different values of graphene oxide concentration (b).

Strength tests of concrete with rGO suspensions – 7 days (Fig. 11 and 12)

Measurement value	Control sample	Sample + modifier	0,02 %	0,05 %	0,07 %
Mass of a cube, g	2342	2346	2323	2312	2322
Average weight, g	2339	2346	2325	2327	2342
Density, g/cm ³	2,34	2,35	2,32	2,31	2,32
P1, MPa	32,78	44,68	33,01	34,41	35,7
P2, MPa	32,74	42,17	35,55	33,17	33,7
P _{avg} , MPa	32,78	43,43	34,28	33,79	34,7
P _{ref1} , %		3,35	4,64	3,14	5,92
P _{ref2} , %		1,33	1,05	1,03	1,06

Figure 11. - Tabulated results of strength tests of samples with reduced graphene oxide

Figure 12. - Relative error (P_{rel}) of the strength of samples with rGO depending on the control (a); dependence of the relative strength (P_{rel2}) in compression at different values of the concentration of reduced graphene oxide (b).

Final values of sample strength and the strength dependence curve on GO concentration – 14 days (Fig. 13 and 14).

Measurement value	Control sample	0,02 %	0,05 %	0,07 %
Mass of a cube, g	2264	2261	2313	2277
Average weight, g	2260	2280	2301	2290
Density, g/cm ³	2,260	2,280	2,302	2,290
P1, MPa	26,55	30,77	33,95	29,91
P2, MPa	26,20	31,69	32,79	34,92
P _{avg} , MPa	26,38	31,23	33,37	32,42
P _{ref1} , %		18,41	26,52	22,90
P _{ref2} , %		1,18	1,27	1,23

Figure 13. - Tabulated results of strength tests of samples with graphene oxide.

Figure 14. - Relative error (P_{rel}) of the strength of samples with GO depending on the control (a); dependence of the relative strength (P_{rel2}) on compression at different values of graphene oxide concentration (b).

As a result of the work, the following patterns were revealed:

1. Compressive strength of cube samples aged 1-7 days increased from 13 to 63%, at the age of 14 days by 16-62% relative to the control samples. Based on the results of determining the effect of graphene oxide suspension on concrete, it can be concluded that the surface of graphene or graphene oxide is energy-active and can act as a crystallization center.

2. This effect is fully manifested at a graphene concentration (solid substance) equal to (0.05 - 0.07)% of the concrete mixture.

3. The method of introducing a suspension of graphene or graphene oxide by dispersion in water can be used in the technological cycle of obtaining concrete mixtures in production.

Model of graphite splitting with cluster water

To obtain the suspension shown in Fig. 8a, it is necessary to split the graphite. For this purpose, we have developed a method of splitting graphite with microcluster water [20-24]. In these works, experimental results were obtained for the first time, indicating the intercalation of graphite by microcluster water (MCW) in centrifugal and electric fields with the formation of graphene nanostructures (Fig. 15).

Figure 15. - Graphene nanostructures obtained using MCW

Since no changes were observed in distilled water, the studies [20-24] concluded that intercalation of “microclusters” into the interlayer space of graphite occurs, causing its expansion from 3.44 Å to 6 Å and increasing this expansion in some places with prolonged exposure. Fig. 16b shows the same vessels after 80 minutes of ex-

posure to an alternating electric field of 500 V (frequency 50 Hz). Room temperature 22 °C. It is evident that the level of the MCW has decreased (vessel on the left), and the volume of the decrease is comparable to the volume of graphite, which indicates that the introduction of MCW into a significant part of the interlayer space of graphite has occurred.

Figure 16. - Vessels with graphite before exposure to an electric field. On the left is MCW, on the right is distilled water (a); Vessels after exposure to a field of 500 V, 50 Hz, 80 minutes at 22 °C (b); On the left is a vessel with graphite in MCF, on the right in distilled water after an electric field at 30 °C (c).

It is visually observed that the graphite particles have swollen, which also confirms the fact of effective introduction of water into the interlayer space. A repeated experiment conducted at a temperature of 30 °C led to the fact that the graphite exfoliated, with the formation of abundant black foam, which floated above the water (Fig. 16c). Since the density of graphene with a plate thickness of up to 4 nm is 40 g/liter, with a thickness of up to 10 nm is 260 g/liter, it can be assumed that the foam consists of graphene. Thus, a slight increase in temperature led to the swollen graphite beginning to delaminate, with layers being carried to the surface of the water.

When splitting graphite with aqueous solutions, cracks that form in any solid obtained by any method in nature or artificially were not taken into account. This is due to the presence of a surface in a solid and a surface layer associated with it, the thickness of which is 2-6 nm and differs from the properties of the rest of the volume. In this case, the surface layer is characterized by anisotropy.

Let us consider a model of the transport flow of an aqueous solution through graphite placed in a cylindrical glass in centrifugal or ultrasonic fields. An aqueous solution with a density $\rho(r,z,t)$, which moves according

to the dependence $\beta(t)$ in a cylinder with the corresponding coordinate system, can be described by the diffusion equation:

$$\frac{\partial \rho(r, z, t)}{\partial t} = D \left[\frac{\partial^2 \rho(r, z, t)}{\partial z^2} + \frac{1}{r} \cdot \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(r \frac{\partial \rho(r, z, t)}{\partial r} \right) \right]$$

where D is the diffusion coefficient of the solution.

We will choose the conditions on the boundary and the initial condition in the form:

$$\begin{aligned} \rho(r, z, t)|_{t=0} &= \varphi(r, z), \\ \rho(r, z, t)|_{r=R} &= \gamma(z, t), \\ \rho(r, z, t)|_{z=0} &= \gamma_1(r, t), \\ \rho(r, z, t)|_{z=\beta(t)} &= \gamma_2(r, t), \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

Problem (1)-(2) is mathematically similar to our problem [25]. Solving it in a similar way, taking into account some details that we omit, we finally obtain:

$$\begin{aligned} \rho(r, z, t) = J_0 \left(\frac{2r}{R} \right) e^{-a^2 t} & \left\{ \frac{e^2 J_0 \left(\frac{2r}{R} \right)}{16a^3} \ln t + \frac{L J_1 \left(\frac{2r}{R} \right)}{16a^3} e^{-a^2 t} \ln(t-1) + \right. \\ & \left. + \left(1 - \frac{1}{\sqrt{t}} \right) \left(\frac{a^2}{z\pi} + \frac{a^3}{\pi^2 z \beta(t)} \right) + \left(1 - \frac{1}{\sqrt{t}} \right) \frac{2a}{\sqrt{\pi}} \frac{1}{[z - \beta(t)]} \right\}, \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

If time t is very large, then as a result we will get:

$$\rho(r, z, t) = \frac{D^{3/2}}{\pi^2} J_0 \left(\frac{2r}{R} \right) \cdot \frac{t}{z \beta(t)}, \quad (4)$$

Let us denote $z = v t$, where v is the flow velocity, t is the time of its movement. We shall assume the phase separation movement to be self-similar $\beta(t) = \beta_0 t$. We shall use the asymptotic representation of Bessel functions, then at $r = R$ we finally obtain:

$$\rho(r, z, t) = \frac{D^{3/2}}{\pi^{5/2}} \cdot \frac{1}{v \cdot \beta_0 \cdot t}, \quad (5)$$

Above, $v(z, t)$ is the velocity of the solution at point z at time t. Assuming that $v(z, t)$ depends only on the density ρ , we have that when the crack is empty ($= 0$), the solution moves with a maximum velocity $v = v_{\max}$. When the crack is filled, the velocity drops to a complete stop ($v = 0$), when $\rho = \rho_{\max}$. Mathematically, this will look like this:

$$\rho = \rho_{\max} \left(1 - \frac{v}{v_{\max}} \right), \quad 0 \leq v \leq v_{\max}. \quad (6)$$

Relations (5) and (6) are shown in Fig. 17..

Figure 17. - Dependence of flow density on the speed of solution movement (a), dependence of flow density on time (b).

From formula (5) we can see a significant dependence of the solution flow density on the diffusion coefficient, i.e. on its rheology, which is equal, according to the classical Newtonian theory - $D = \nu$, where ν is the kinematic viscosity coefficient. We will consider the issue of solution viscosity from the standpoint of the thermodynamic approach developed by us in [26].

As a response function in [26] we take the kinematic viscosity ν , then we will have:

$$\nu = \frac{kT}{c} \cdot \frac{W}{G^0} \cdot \bar{N}, \quad (7)$$

where $\bar{N}kT = PV = (V=1) = P$ is the pressure in the solution flow; W is the kinetic energy of the particles (molecules) of the solution $W = m V^2/2$; G^0 is the energy of the mixture (solution); c = const, m is the mass of the particles, V is their speed.

Equation (7) will take the form (Fig. 18a):

$$\nu = \frac{1}{c} \cdot \frac{P}{2G_{cm}^0} \cdot mV^2. \quad (8)$$

Considering that $G^0 = \gamma S$, S is the area, we obtain the following equation for the relationship between the viscosity of the solution and its surface tension γ (Fig. 18b):

$$\nu = \frac{J}{\gamma}, \quad (9)$$

where J is the liquid constant under given thermodynamic conditions. Equation (9) is also valid for graphite, according to which the solution flow is proportional to the surface energy of graphite $\gamma = W_a/2$, where W_a is the adhesion energy of graphite.

Figure 18. Theoretical dependences of kinematic viscosity on pressure for some liquids (a), illustration of formula (9).

Let us rewrite formula (5) as follows:

$$W_p = \cdot 10^3 \cdot \sqrt{\frac{L_C}{M \cdot \nu \cdot t}} \cdot \frac{L_C}{M \cdot \nu \cdot t}, \tag{10}$$

Here for aqueous solutions $J = 2 \cdot 10^{-8}$, $\beta_0 = 0.2$.

In formula (10), all parameters on the right-hand side are determined experimentally and yield the value of W_p . If the value of $W_p > W_{ac}$, then graphite is split to form graphene.

Model of cracks in graphene concrete

Concrete consists of cement paste, which is a porous and hierarchical material with different phases.

When cement powder is mixed with water, the hydration reaction leads to the formation of the main chemical products: calcium silicate hydrate (C–S–H), calcium hydroxide (CH), ettringite, and monosulfoaluminate. C–S–H occupies approximately 70% of the fully hydrated products and makes the main contribution to the mechanical strength of the material [27]. Silicate phases react with water to form calcium hydroxide and a rigid calcium silicate hydrate gel, C–S–H gel [28]:

The thickness of the surface layer of a solid $R(I)$ and the length of nanocracks L_{nm} are given by the formula [29]:

$$R(I) = L_{nm} = 0,17 \cdot 10^{-9} \cdot \alpha \cdot \nu \text{ [m]}. \tag{13}$$

In equation (13) it is necessary to know one parameter – the molar volume of the element, which is equal to $\nu = M/\rho$ (M is the molar mass, ρ is its density), $\alpha = 1 \text{ mol m}^{-2}$ is a constant to maintain the dimensionality ($R(I)$ [m]). Considering that the rigid calcium silicate gel of the C–S–H hydrate is a homogeneous solid solution, it is easy to estimate the molar mass from equations (11) and (12) – $M_1 = 1070 \text{ g/mol}$; $M_2 = 922 \text{ g/mol}$. The crystal structure obtained from equation (12) is closer to the mineral tobermorite [30], which is

a layered crystalline form of calcium silicate. The density of the C–S–H gel is closely related to the water content in the pores of the gel. Neutron and X-ray scattering methods were used to determine with high accuracy [31] the density and water content of saturated globules. The density is 2.604 g/cm^3 ,

The thickness of the surface layer of the C–S–H gel according to equation (13) is equal to $L_{nm} = R(I) = 60.3 \text{ nm}$, and the number of layers $n = R(I)/a$ (a is the interlayer distance, equal to $a = 1.4 \text{ nm}$ [28]). This means that the number of C–S–H layers is $n = 43$. According to our work [29], the diagram of the crystalline form of calcium silicate will look like that shown in Fig. 19a, and the silicate chain (monolayer of calcium silicate) is shown in Fig. 19b.

Figure 19. Schematic diagram of a solid: nanolayer → mesolayer → bulk phase (a); schematic diagram of a C–S–H layer showing a Ca–O core layer with a silicate tetrahedron attached on both sides. The silicate chain, calcium octahedron and oxygen atoms are shown as dark blue, light blue tetrahedron and red spheres, respectively (b) [28].

The thickness of the surface layer of the gel and the length of the C–S–H nanocracks are equal to $L_{nm} = R(I) = 60.3 \text{ nm}$ ($< 100 \text{ nm}$), i.e. it represents a nanostructure according to Gleiter [32]. The length of the nanocrack in equation (13) reflects the feature that it is associated not only with the geometry of the crystal lattices, but also with the physical properties of the crystals, namely: with the type of chemical bond; porosity, anisotropy and other properties. If we consider Fig. 19a, then in [33] we showed that the evolution of nanocracks occurs according to the law:

$$L_C = 10^2 L_{\mu m} = 10^4 L_{nm} = 0,17 \cdot 10^{-5} \cdot M / \rho [\text{m}]. \quad (14)$$

where L_{nm} , $L_{\mu m}$, L_C – length of nanocracks, mesocracks and critical length of cracks before destruction of a solid.

So, for standard concrete: $L_{nm} = 60 \text{ nm}$; $L_{\mu m} = 6 \text{ microns}$; $L_C = 0.6 \text{ mm}$. These data are typical without external load, without changes in the environment (temperature, humidity, etc.). Fig. 20 shows the kinetic diagram of fatigue destruction of artillery barrels [34] (in our case, concrete). In this case, the initial and final sections represent a linear function.

Figure 20. Kinetic diagram of concrete destruction [34].

The diagram shown in Fig. 20 is an S-curve similar to the line from the catastrophe theory [35]. If we take the function $L(N)$ as the coordinate of the concrete destruction process, where N is the number of cracks, and select the concrete density ρ and $G/F(I)$ as the control parameters, where G is the shear modulus ($G = 65 \text{ GPa}$ for concrete), $F(I)$ is the Peierls-Nabarro barrier ($F(I) = 76 \cdot 10^{-9} \text{ Pa}$ for concrete), then we obtain the equation:

$$L(N) = 0.25N^4 - 0.5\rho N^2 - G/F(I) \cdot N. \quad (15)$$

Let us move on to a dynamic system in equation (15), that is, we will consider the crack as a gradient function:

$$\frac{dL(N)}{dt} = \frac{\partial L(N)}{\partial N} = N^3 - \rho N - G/F(I) = 0. \quad (16)$$

Equation (16) is analytically similar to the equation of classical mechanics for the motion of a body in a viscous friction medium. The process of transition from one state to another is smooth, similar to an S-shaped curve (Fig. 20). Calculating equation (16) using Cardan's formula, we obtain for the number of cracks in concrete $N \approx 10^7$, characteristic of the mesolayer.

The middle part of the curve II in Fig. 20 was first described by Paris [36]:

$$\frac{dL(N)}{dt} = C(\Delta K)^4, \quad (17)$$

where K is the stress intensity factor per cycle; C is the material constant. Both of these values should be determined experimentally.

Equation (14) shows: the number of cracks in concrete in the nanostructure region I is 10^5 , in the mesoscopic region II is 10^7 , and in the pre-destruction region III is about 10^9 .

Since nanocracks always form when a surface layer is formed in a solid, it is possible to come up with a case of crack inhibition. This area includes modification of concrete by diluting cement with mineral nanopowders, among which, at present, graphene nanopowders are occupied [37]. We also obtained results in [38] on improving the properties of concrete (reducing nanocracks) with the addition of graphene obtained by liquid-phase exfoliation of graphite [39]. The structure of C–S–H obtained by molecular dynamics (MD) [28] with graphene (G) and graphene oxide (GO) is shown in Fig. 21.

Figure 21. Structure of G/C-S-H and GO/C-S-H [28]

It can be seen from Fig. 21 that graphene and graphene oxide are embedded in the interlayer space. Graphene and GO confined in the interlayer region of C-S-H gel show different morphologies. In graphene, the carbon atoms ordered in the xy plane are distributed away from the C-S-H surface. No expansion along the z-direction is observed at the graphene/C-S-H interface in Fig. 21a. On the other hand, as shown in Fig. 21b, the protruding hydroxyls on both sides of GO indicate the C-S-H interface. The C-C bonds in GO are stretched in the z-direction, and the graphene sheet is broken to some extent.

Compared with standard concrete, the R(I) and R(II) values are halved and the elastic parameters of concrete are changed. The addition of graphene and graphene oxide to cement mortar significantly strengthens standard concrete (4-5 times) and reduces the amount of nanocracks.

Conclusion

The following regularities were revealed as a result of experimental studies:

1. Compressive strength of cube samples aged 1-7 days increased from 13 to 63%, at the age of 14 days by 16-62% relative to the control samples. Based on the results of determining the effect of graphene oxide suspension on concrete, it can be concluded that the surface of graphene or graphene oxide is energy-active and can act as a crystallization center.
2. This effect is fully manifested at a graphene concentration (solid substance) equal to (0.05 - 0.07)% of the concrete mixture.
3. The method of introducing a suspension of graphene or graphene oxide by dispersion in water can be used in the technological cycle of obtaining concrete mixtures in production.

To obtain the equation of graphite splitting with aqueous solutions, one can use the theory of catastrophes with suitable control parameters.

The theory of cracks began to develop in the 20s of the last century and continues to develop to this day. A number of models of crack formation are presented in reviews [1-9]: Griffiths, Zener-Straw-Petch, Cottrell, Ballough-Gilman, Orvan-Straw, Koble, Nabarro-Herring and some others. However, none of the models present calculation of crack length and its evolution. Our

model shows that any body with a surface cannot be represented as an unlimited body - a technique known from classical mechanics. Cracks do not occur there. The difference in the interaction of near-surface atoms from atoms inside a solid leads to the occurrence of nanocracks, the evolution of which under certain conditions leads to the destruction of the solid. Our model, which is in development, allows us to determine the length of cracks in solids.

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